

CATCHING UP THROUGH LINKAGES WITH FIES: AN ANALYSIS OF VIETNAMESE LATECOMER FIRMS

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Abstract: *This study tries to identify the ideal characteristics of Vietnamese enterprises, which firms are better positioned to leverage linkages with FIEs, and how “near” the other firms are to the ideal characteristics. In doing so, ideal objectives for government catch-up measures, support, and policy and management implications will be defined. This will be achieved by computing a distance vector between a sample of Vietnamese businesses from the Vietnamese enterprise competitiveness survey and the ideal Vietnamese business. The results state that catching up is a prevalent notion for local firms in developing countries. Spillovers from foreign direct investment (FDI) are essential to developing domestic businesses in this regard since they provide significant “learning opportunities.” As such, firms should have to profit from technological spillovers and links to foreign and foreign-invested enterprises, as well as the practices that should be encouraged and pursued, based on a comprehensive analysis of the start-up cluster. Such outcomes have substantial ramifications for both public policy and administrative activities. The data clarifies why the highest-performing cluster is referred to as starters and why these enterprises should be the primary focus of capacity-building strategies. Concerning the other two clusters, authors highlight two intriguing findings that may be indicators of the possible ‘internal’ readiness of spectators to perform at the same level as starters.*

Keywords: *Absorptive capacity, Catch-up strategy, Spillover, Technology strategy, Vietnamese enterprises.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Local companies in emerging areas must “catch up” because foreign-invested enterprises (FIEs) have substantial first-mover advantages in creating new technology and winning market share (Li

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and Wang, 2021). The catch-up strategy refers to the strategic approach used by organizations, often known as corporations, to reduce or eliminate inequalities in technology and market share compared to established competitors within a certain period (Enderwick and Buckley, 2021). Local enterprises have generally used two methods to catch up with FIEs. The first was to use foreignness liabilities to produce goods, services, or business models based on a strong grasp of the local environment that these FIEs cannot readily replicate (Lee and Malerba, 2017). Secondly, local enterprises transmit and absorb FIE technology to strengthen manufacturing capabilities (Choi, 2019). However, FIEs can now understand local ecosystems and may decide not to transfer sophisticated technology, especially if local enterprises are rivals. Thus, local firms must offer new ways to catch up with this cutting-edge growth, which demands internal resources and international company cooperation.

Since 1986's "Doi moi" economic reform, Vietnam has attracted FDI (Ta et al., 2020). Vietnam has attracted 8,000 foreign direct investment projects with a total registered investment capital of over USD145 billion and 7,500 local investment projects with a total registered capital of over VND970 trillion (Hoang et al., 2021). FDI has demonstrated its importance to the Vietnamese economy. Vietnam is attracting record FDI (Ta et al., 2020). Foreign-invested firms immediately impact the economy's and local enterprises' growth by boosting competition pressure, pressing business efficiency, fostering technology diffusion and transfer, etc. Therefore, the Vietnamese policy focuses on catching up and increasing output. However, Vietnam's catch-up rate is slower than in the past, which is caused by ineffective technical transmission. Inefficiency is associated with absorptive capacity gaps and other variables that impede production growth (Vietnam National Productivity Master Plan, 2020). Low school enrolment (low-skilled workforce), huge differences in labor productivity between FIEs and local firms, and ineffective innovation and R&D expenditures all underscore Vietnam's vulner-

ability. Increasing local enterprises' exposure to global knowledge and technology flows through FDI and trade is the first step to linking export-driven and innovation-driven growth. FIEs control Vietnamese exports, particularly high-tech ones (up to 60% in the manufacturing sector). This "dual economic structure" concentrates Vietnamese firms' output and exports on low-tech FIEs in Vietnam have a worse relationship with local enterprises than in other neighboring nations (Nguyen et al., 2019).

A learning-by-internationalization strategy can bridge these gaps and improve local enterprises' contacts with FIEs (Gattai, 2015). However, the variety of businesses' competence leads to varied preparation and capacities of domestic enterprises to maximize FIE links (Petti et al., 2020; Driffield et al., 2014). Domestic firms with superior connections and absorptive ability are best positioned to learn and catch up. Identifying and concentrating on these enterprises may help the government enhance productivity and innovation. This article identifies the ideal features of such organizations and evaluates, using a Vietnamese sample, which companies are better positioned to leverage links with FIEs and how "far" the other companies are from the ideal. This will identify appropriate targets for government catch-up measures, support them, as well as draw policy and managerial consequences. An unique econometric technique, detailed in the third part, will show the current similarities and differences among Vietnamese firms. By comparing 2970 enterprises to the ideal corporation to define their behaviors, this ideal corporation will show how far a company is from meeting the benchmark.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Technology spillovers from foreign-invested enterprises (FIEs)

Technology spillover from FIEs and local enterprises in an economy can boost domestic firms' efficiency and productivity (Ascani and Gagliardi, 2020). FIEs can enable domestic enterprises through technology spillover, which is the most crucial enterprise relation-

ship (Olayinka and Loykulnanta, 2019). Informal spillovers spread knowledge without a contractual relationship (Meyer, 2004). In other words, global firms and domestic enterprises with a strategic partnership or formal collaboration experience spillovers. “Knowledge flows” have no paper record, making spillovers hard to monitor. Knowledge connections with foreign investment enterprises are externally handled and internally recombined into new goods, techniques, processes, routines, and practices (Makhloufi et al., 2021). According to Olayinka and Loykulnanta (2019), global firms overflow into domestic enterprises in many ways. First, domestic companies may absorb cutting-edge technologies by watching international organizations. Second, foreign-invested firms bring worldwide experience to local firms. Third, foreign-invested firms may unknowingly share information with local enterprises if they use the same suppliers, distributors, and trade groups. Last but not least, domestic companies must update their technologies to escape “fresh gusts of competition” from global firms. FIEs bridge the technology gap between industrialized and developing nations since they have the funding for research and development; as such, FIEs in emerging economies invent most new, advanced technology and equipment (Ascani and Gagliardi, 2020). MNEs headquarters provide sophisticated technology to their affiliates or subsidiary FIEs in the host nation, which employs it as their unique investment for competitive advantage (Hoang et al., 2021).

2.2. Absorptive capacity of latecomer firms

The term “absorptive capacity” refers to the dynamic capability that exists inside companies and makes it possible for one-of-a-kind capability combinations to mutually support one another (Duan et al., 2021; Petti et al., 2020). In addition, absorptive capacity refers to a company’s ability to generate new knowledge and use that knowledge in order to develop other organizational abilities, such as marketing, distribution, and production, depending on the company’s existing body of information (Makhloufi et al., 2021). The absorptive

ability enables organizations to put newly acquired knowledge into practice, hence amplifying the information's rippling effects (Negash et al., 2020). This capability can be crucial for organizations to adapt to international competition and boost productivity. This is because foreign investors may force out local enterprises that lack this expertise, which can result in excess production capacity and low productivity in the short run. Adapting to international competition and boosting productivity are two goals that organizations should have.

2.3. Catch-up strategy and Technology Strategy of latecomer firms

2.3.1. Catch-up strategy

Catch-up strategy is the practice of organizations (usually referred to as companies) minimizing or eliminating technological and market share disparities with incumbents within a certain time frame (Enderwick and Buckley, 2021). For firms in industrialised nations, catch-up is the relative pace in a race along a predetermined trajectory, and their technological development is a cumulative one-way process (Li and Wang, 2021). Catching up, however, is not relative speed in a sprint along a predetermined trajectory for companies in developing nations (Petti et al., 2020). There are two primary distinctions between latecomers in the two economies. First, latecomers in emerging economies are frequently far from sources of technology and research and development in science, engineering, and technology. Second, latecomers in emerging economies are separated from major worldwide markets, which frequently deal with undeveloped local markets and unsophisticated customers. Due to these constraints, the competitive advantage of latecomers in emerging economies remains inferior to that of industrial incumbents in industrialized countries. For these latecomers in emerging markets, discontinuous technological development focused on catching up to or surpassing the incumbents (Li and Wang, 2021). Consequently, latecomers should have advanced adjustments in the technology-focused perspective on economic growth.

2.3.2. Technology strategy

A technology strategy outlines innovation, manufacturing, and customer delivery goals (Vega and Tell, 2021). Lee et al. (2021) describe technology strategy as leveraging technology and technical expertise to develop valuable goods and services, which also shows how technical innovation meets commercial needs. Thus, technology strategy is a portfolio of decisions and strategies a corporation utilizes to manage external technological challenges and possibilities. Technology strategy helps companies acquire, develop, and use technology for competitive advantage (Dasgupta and Gupta, 2014). The firm's technology, interactions with systems, and other network strategies define it. Thus, a technology strategy's purpose must take into account the relative relevance and placement of its internal and external technologies. Moreover, technology strategy does not spontaneously move from production competence to innovation capability or from basic technology adoption to innovation. Thus, late-comer businesses must have technology transfer contracts with foreign-invested enterprises. Technological competency is mostly firm-specific, depending on human resources, technology level, and organizational system management (Teece, 2018).

2.4. Study's Conceptual Framework: FIEs and local firms, from linkage to advantage

On the basis of the factors above we have excerpted a number of factors that may should be in place and help to distinguish companies more prepared to deal with FIEs, organised in the following three-pillared framework, depicted in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Study's conceptual framework

2.4.1. Linkages with FIEs and Absorptive Capacity of latecomer firms

Data from industrialized nations rather than developing or emerging countries has supported technology spillovers (Meyer and Sinani, 2009). Empirical research also found that local enterprises' absorptive ability influences technological spillover (Ha and Giroud, 2015). Foreign businesses (FIEs) might help domestic suppliers improve quality by setting higher standards (Anwar and Nguyen, 2011). Thus, local enterprises need FIE links to handle innovation-related issues. These links depend primarily on the traits and compatibility of the FIEs and host nations. Negash et al. (2020) found that high-absorptive capacity local companies had positive spillovers, while low-absorptive capacity firms had negative spillovers. In the Swiss service and construction business, Hamida (2011) showed that high-tech domestic firms profit from FIE competition, whereas mid- and low-tech enterprises benefit from demonstration effects. However, Turco and Maggioni (2019) explain that information flowing from overseas affiliates depends on internal skills such product-specific knowledge advantage and local businesses' absorptive ability.

Thus, technological spillover requires FIE links and absorptive ability. Domestic enterprises in developing markets may need help to innovate in response to product modifications, new market possibilities, or local restrictions if their innovation capabilities do not match FIE manufacturing capabilities (Subramaniam and Youndt, 2015). Several studies have noted that developing market subsidiaries of multinational businesses adopt strategies to fulfil local market demands, capitalize on home technology advantages, and advance in global value chains (Ryan et al., 2020; Burger et al., 2018). This is why many nations, especially developing and growing economies, offer incentives to multinationals.

2.4.2. Absorptive Capacity and Technology strategy of latecomer firms

In an innovation-based economy, local enterprises in developing markets use technology strategies to meet consumer needs and take advantage of technical catch-up opportunities (Giudice et al., 2019;

Radosevic and Yoruk, 2016). For local enterprises, persistent innovation is more crucial than high capability development (Chen et al., 2022). Foreign-invested corporations must bring innovative technology to the country and adapt it to their unique setting (Buckley et al., 2010). Thus, by observing or engaging with international professionals and workers from foreign companies, local enterprises must learn how to duplicate the new technology or improve their products and marketing efforts (Newman et al., 2015). Importantly, transferring technology to compete on low-cost manufacturing alone no longer works. Thus, local enterprises must create innovation capabilities in each company to learn from foreign investment companies in this globalized period (Petti et al., 2019). This study shows substantial correlations between absorptive capacity and latecomer enterprises' technology catch-up approach. It demonstrates that businesses with strong absorptive capacity profit more from all spillover channels in both nations, whereas firms with low-capacity benefit differentially (Olayinka and Loykulnanta, 2019). Hoang et al. (2021) found that all local enterprise variables—R&D, technology, national policy, etc.—positively affect innovation strategy choices in Vietnam.

3. METHODS

3.1. Sample and Measures

For the analyses, we use a sample of 2970 firms from the 2017 Survey of Vietnamese Enterprises and a set of selected specific questions according to the framework developed as follows: For linkages with Foreign Invested Enterprises (FIEs), we choose questions aimed at detecting the existence and intensity/strength of backward and forward vertical linkages, e.g., with suppliers and customers, and, more specifically.

- Whether technology equipment or machinery are provided by foreign invested enterprises (i.e., Vietnamese domestic firms with foreign investments) or outside Vietnam (foreign enterprises abroad), whether long-term contracts are signed with foreign suppliers, whether the contracts with foreign suppliers contain specif-

ic provisions for technology transfer, and whether the firms have made specific investments for foreign suppliers.

- The number of foreign-invested enterprises as customers or outside Vietnam, whether long-term contracts are signed with foreign customers, whether the contracts with foreign customers contain specific provisions for technology transfer, and whether firms have made specific investments for foreign customers

For absorptive capacity, we choose:

- Whether firms have technology and R&D activities, and from when.

- What kind of technology R&D activities do those firms have (self-research against outsourcing)?

- Whether firms have highly skilled and experienced workers

For technology strategy, we choose:

- What is the goal of technological innovation, and, more specifically, the one geared towards more significant, 'new-to-the-market' innovation or 'new-to-the enterprises' at least?

- What strategies are pursued to increase performance and, again, more specifically, the ones geared towards more significant innovations (for example, expanding operations or product-related at least)?

Ideally, a firm should display the highest values in all of the above questions. This means having several and significant linkages with foreign and foreign-invested enterprises; self-research technology and R&D activities (with a certain tenure) with a high proportion of skilled and experienced employees; and a proactive technology strategy geared towards significant innovation (for example, 'new-to-the-market' product-related and above innovations). That would be the 'ideal' firm taken as a reference for the empirical strategy, detailed below.

3.2. Empirical strategy

The main idea is to classify Vietnamese businesses, starting from the information contained in the dataset. Having a large amount of

data but with many information gaps, it is challenging to implement a classical econometric or statistical methodology. Through the following methodology, we can assign scores to firms, based on a set of questions and answers that we define ourselves, in order to calculate the dissimilarity matrices of firms. The similarity matrices allow us to have a global mapping of the behavior of companies in the innovation field. Furthermore, by adding an “ideal” firm, we could move from distance matrices to distance vectors, and this will allow us to reliably define clusters.

Based on the clusters (we could identify three: good companies (green), medium-sized companies (yellow), bad companies (Red)) we have a chromatic scale to be able to give important policy indications. Furthermore, this tool will be useful if you want to add a company ex post and evaluate its position within one of the clusters.

The distance vector will also tell us how far a firm is from the ideal firm. Furthermore, by defining the weaknesses, we can trace an individualized improvement path. The distance vector, constructed in this way, is a flexible tool that takes into account the heterogeneity of firms.

We consider a set of $N \in \mathbb{N}$ companies and a set of $Q \in \mathbb{N}$ questions. Given any two companies $i, j = 1, \dots, N$, we aim at measuring some kind of distance d_{ij} between company i and company j according to how different their answers are. We now construct such a metric with a top-down approach.

First, it is reasonable to assume that such a distance is question-wise additive, i.e.

$$d_{ij} = \sum_{q=1}^Q d_{ij;q}, \quad (1)$$

where $d_{ij;q}$ is a distance measure between companies i and j according to the q -th question. Moreover, we require that each question has the same weight, hence the question-wise distances $d_{ij;q}$ we are about to define are normalized to range in $[0; 1]$. Now, questions are subdivided into four groups:

$Q^c \in \mathbb{N}$ questions with single categorical answer;

$Q^s \in \mathbb{N}$ questions with single ordered answer;

$Q^m \in \mathbb{N}$ questions with multiple categorical answer;

$Q^p \in \mathbb{N}$ questions with permutation answers,

so that: $Q = Q^c + Q^s + Q^m + Q^p$ and

$$d_{ij} = \sum_{c=1}^{Q^c} d_{ij;c} + \sum_{s=1}^{Q^s} d_{ij;s} + \sum_{m=1}^{Q^m} d_{ij;m} + \sum_{p=1}^{Q^p} d_{ij;p} \quad (2)$$

We are thus left to define the question-wise distances $d_{ij;c}$, $d_{ij;s}$, $d_{ij;m}$ and $d_{ij;p}$.

For questions with single categorical answer, assume that company i and j 's answers to question c are c_i and c_j . Then we define:

$$d_{ij;c} := \delta(c_i, c_j), \quad (3)$$

where $\delta(c_i, c_j)$ is the Kronecker delta symbol. In other words, the distance between firms i and j according to question c is 0 if their respective answers coincide and 1 otherwise.

For questions with single ordered answer, say question s , assume that there are $a(s)$ possible answers ordered in ascending order, and we assign rankings $\rho_1, \rho_2, \dots, \rho_{a(s)}$ to these answers. Assume now that companies i and j 's answers to question s are $s(i)$ and $s(j)$, respectively. Then it is reasonable to define

$$d_{ij;s} := |\rho_{s(i)} - \rho_{s(j)}|, \quad (4)$$

i.e. the distance between companies i and j according to question s is the absolute difference of their respective answers' rankings.

For questions with multiple categorical answers, say question m , assume that there are $a(m)$ tickable answers. For any $a = 1, \dots, a(m)$ we say that $i_a = 1$ or $i_a = 0$ if company i did or did not tick answer a , respectively. We then define

$$d(ij; m) := \frac{1}{a(m)} \sum_{a=1}^{a(m)} \delta(i_a, j_a), \quad (5)$$

where $\delta(i_a, j_a)$ is again the Kronecker delta symbol.

A question with *permutation answers* is a question whose answers are to be ranked. Assume question p has $a(p)$ answers to be ranked. Assume that firm i ranks each answer $a = 1, \dots, a(p)$ at i_a -th place. We then define

$$d(ij; p) := \frac{1}{\sigma(a(p))} \sum_{a=1}^{a(p)} |i_a - j_a|, \quad (6)$$

where $\sigma(a(p))$ is the maximum value that the above sum can possibly reach.

For instance, $\sigma(6) = 18$.

We end up with the following formula:

$$d_{ij} = \sum_{c=1}^{Q^c} \delta(c_i, c_j) + \sum_{s=1}^{Q^s} |\rho_{s(i)} - \rho_{s(j)}| + \sum_{m=1}^{Q^m} \sum_{a=1}^{a(m)} \frac{\delta(i_a, j_a)}{a(m)} + \sum_{p=1}^{Q^p} \sum_{a=1}^{a(p)} \frac{|i_a - j_a|}{\sigma(a(p))}. \quad (7)$$

4. RESULTS

The technique outlined above enables us to establish three distinct clusters of businesses based on a score representing their distance from the “ideal” firm, as shown in Figure 2. The ‘ideal’ firm is one that has multiple and significant links with foreign and foreign-invested enterprises; self-research technology and R&D activities with a high proportion of skilled and experienced employees; and a proactive technology strategy geared toward significant innovation (for example, ‘new-to-market’ product-related and above innovations). Using a kernel Weibull, figure 2 depicts the distribution of the businesses into three clusters, with a traffic-light chromatic scale ranging from green to red to indicate the proximity of the clusters in terms of the aforementioned criteria. The horizontal axis indicates the normalized distance value from the ideal firm, with 0 being the shortest distance and 1 representing the greatest distance, while the vertical axis reflects the number of businesses.

Specifically, green bars show organizations whose distance from the ‘ideal’ firm is less than 26, equivalent to the 100th company with the greatest gap. According to a preparation perspective and using the metaphor of a running race, we refer to these organizations as “starters.”

Yellow bars represent companies with a distance between 26.01 and 31 from the top company. Using the same perspective and language, we refer to these businesses as observers. Lastly, red bars indicate the firms whose distance from the “ideal” firm is more than 31.01. We can refer to these firms as outsiders because they do not participate in the game. We chose these cutoffs by splitting the remaining score into two equal (and complete) sections.

Figure 2: Firms' Clusters

Following the conceptual structure of the study, we provide the results for each pillar, focusing on the features of the cluster of beginners and contrasting significant findings with those of the other two clusters to show the contrasts between the three groups. Regarding backward connections with suppliers, we discovered that only 8% of start-ups purchase technical equipment or machinery from International Invested Firms in Vietnam, and the percentage of partnerships with foreign enterprises outside Vietnam is considerably smaller (95% do not have any partners from abroad). 18% of start-ups have signed long-term contracts (36 months or more) with overseas raw materials and intermediate inputs suppliers, and around 48% of

these contracts include knowledge transfer arrangements. For 35% of long-term agreements, particular investments are made, but it is difficult to establish which were made specifically for foreign contracts.

Figure 3: Contract accompanied by technology transfer provisions (starters)

These percentages are lower for the other two groupings, with 16% of spectators' long-term contracts featuring technology transfer clauses and 2% of outsiders' long-term contracts containing technology transfer clauses. This drop demonstrates that, among virtues, there is a high emphasis on technology transfer, particularly from international suppliers to domestic enterprises. Regarding the forward linkages with customers, the relationship is incredibly intense, with about a quarter of the most important customers (23%) being FIEs and about a third of the 54% of firms with long-term contacts, including technology transfer provisions from customers to enterprises, being with customers outside Vietnam.

This scenario is even murkier when it comes to particular investments relating to clients outside of Vietnam: 22% of start-up companies reported having made specific investments, while 78% either did not respond or did not provide a response. Comparatively, only 7% of spectator companies and 0.5% of outsiders disclose such technology transfer provisions. This characteristic reveals the distinctions between the selected groupings.

In accordance with the pillar of absorptive capacity, a sizable proportion (66%) of the beginning enterprises' cluster engages in Technology and R&D activities with a duration of around ten years (the average starting year for these activities in this cluster is 2007). In contrast, onlookers and outsiders engage in far less technological and R&D activities (respectively 21,2% and 0.2%) and have less experience (respectively 9 years and 6 years). Forty percent of newcomers conduct self-research, while 25% conduct both self-research and out-source. All of these appear to corroborate the rule earlier is better.

40% of enterprises in the startup cluster use highly-skilled and seasoned employees. In contrast, this number is less than 30% in the cluster of spectators and less than 20% in the cluster of foreigners. Intriguingly, shorter distances, as opposed to links with FIE pillars, may be observed, revealing a potential preparation that can be leveraged, as discussed further in the discussion section.

In terms of technology strategy, the startups' cluster is characterized by an ambitious strategy, with 40% of firms aiming for new-to-the-market technological innovation, nearly doubling the 23% aiming for new-to-the-enterprise technological innovation, and even 3% aiming for new-to-the-world technological innovation, demonstrating a solid commitment to innovation (figure 4).

Figure 4: Goal of technology innovation (starters)

Start-ups' strategy for enhancing performance is complementary to their innovation-driven ethos. 36% of them want to extend corporate operations into a new business or production field com-

mensurate with the 'new-to-market' technological innovation approach, with nearly all of them intending to improve product and process quality (respectively 92% and 93%). The gathering of on-lookers is pretty close (88% of the whole aims at improving product and 86% aims at improving process quality). The opposite is true for foreigners (respectively 65% and 74%).

5. DISCUSSION

By framing these characteristics as best practices, it outlined the characteristics that firms should have to profit from technological spillovers and links to foreign and foreign-invested enterprises, as well as the practices that should be encouraged and pursued, based on a comprehensive analysis of the start-ups cluster. Such outcomes have substantial ramifications for both public policy and administrative activities. The data clarifies why the highest performing cluster is referred to as starters and why these enterprises should be the primary focus of capacity-building strategies in Vietnam. Concerning the other two clusters, authors highlight two intriguing findings that may be indicators of the possible 'internal' readiness of spectators to perform at the same level as starters.

First, fewer start-ups have customer-specific investments than supplier-specific ones. This may be, on the one hand, an indication of being mired at the bottom of the Global Value Chain, where their foreign customers have very simple and standardized needs (Ryan et al., 2020; Nguyen et al., 2019). Whereas a more unique or sophisticated request would have necessitated a greater investment. This is a negative indication. However, improved data about supplier-specific investments may indicate ongoing innovation efforts, mainly on product and process.

Second, another indicator is the increased gap in absorptive ability between these companies and FIEs. This may indicate the preparedness or prodromal availability to advance to the next stage, initiating beneficial contacts with locally foreign-invested Vietnam-

ese businesses, primarily as suppliers and secondarily as partners (Petti et al., 2020; Ha and Giroud, 2015).

Cloning does not constitute catching up (Lee and Malerba, 2017). In reality, enterprises and nations execute operations differently, resulting in the emergence of an indigenous process of learning and competence development. Organizational, managerial, and institutional parts of productive practices are frequently the most challenging to imitate and must be tailored to local conditions, norms, and values (Vega and Tell, 2021). These studies focus on beginning conditions, macro factors (such as labor prices and currency rates), business capabilities, and national innovation systems. However, the conceptual framework for evaluating consecutive catch-ups must go beyond these explanations since catch-up factors vary among industries and firms. As a result of a local process of learning and competence development, firms and nations that are catching up may engage in activities that differ from those chosen by the leaders. In other words, these methods for catching up adapt and alter with time. The latecomers participating in this process may pursue distinct technology and product development trajectories, position themselves differently along the catching up ladder, and vary among themselves (Li and Wang, 2021).

For instance, Huawei's catch-up plan involves a "holistic" approach. Specifically, whereas other companies typically concentrate their customer-relationship management efforts on managers, particularly high-level managers, Huawei seeks to develop close working relationships with employees at all levels, believing that ordinary employees can play crucial roles in establishing strong relationships between companies (Gao, 2018). In addition, Asian firms (such as Samsung, LG, and Hyundai-Kia Motors in Korea, MediaTek and AUO in Taiwan, and Huawei in China) have demonstrated that technological laggards can overcome disadvantages and use latecomer-specific advantages to catch up with incumbent, first-mover firms in developed nations (Song, 2016). This phrase refers to the economic variables that

dictate technical progress and innovation trajectory. The technical environment influences how industry-specific patterns of innovation and technological catch-up vary. Therefore, industrial policy or features, technological innovation capabilities, and company's strategic mode are crucial factors to consider when analyzing a local firm's plan to absorb advanced knowledge (Li and Wang, 2021)

6. RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

Latecomer enterprises differ in their levels of preparation and preparedness; hence, policies should be tailored based on this degree. Therefore, managers must be made aware of their own standing in order to intervene in the correct spot and with critical levers, since no one (policymakers included) understands their businesses better than they do.

In terms of theoretical contributions, it is vital for future researches to focus on the intra-firm dynamics of local enterprises, particularly the technology strategy and other catch-up techniques. Therefore, researchers should shift their attention from MNEs in newly industrialized countries to local firms, focusing on the effects of the external and internal business environment on catch-up processes, barriers, and how these firms can take advantage of knowledge access to overcome these barriers. In addition, understanding firms' technology needs is extremely restricted, particularly in emerging nations such as Vietnam (Nguyen et al., 2019). Moreover, according to a Scopus and Web of Science, Vietnam is not among the leading nations conducting essential research on technology strategy, catch-up strategy, and spillover effects between multinational corporations and local enterprises. Since the 1990s, Vietnam has witnessed a continuous decline in the number of state-owned firms due to its status as a developing nation. Meanwhile, the government has enacted business legislation to encourage foreign direct investment (FDI) and increase the economy's openness (Petti et al., 2017). Vietnam has aggressively utilized the mechanisms of production networks created by multinational corporations and has

begun its industrialization process due to foreign direct investment. This contrasts with the industrialization models of other Asian nations, such as Japan, Taiwan, and South Korea, where the growth of indigenous enterprises and industries was the focal point (Kimura and Obashi, 2016). Consequently, another study need is the research scope, in which the Vietnam market and domestic companies should be recognized as outstanding destinations for research on catch-up strategies and technology spillover.

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